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IN SILICO EVALUATION OF TETRAHYMENA PYRIFORMIS TOXICITY FOR TWO SERIES OF NOVEL SUCCINIMIDE DERIVATIVES

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Abstract

An important issue in environmental protection is risk assessment of pollutants and hazardous chemicals including pharmaceuticals. Tetrahymena species are model organism in toxicological assessment of xenobiotics extensively used in various toxicological and environmental studies. Quantitative structure–toxicity relationship (QSTR) models are often applied as green alternatives for predicting the toxicological potential of newly synthesized compounds. In this study 24 newly synthesized succinimide derivatives were evaluated for Tetrahymena pyriformis toxicity in silico. Online tools pkCSM was applied for determining the concentration of the compounds required to inhibit 50% growth of T. pyriformis. Online tools SwissADME and PreADMET were applied to determine the physicochemical descriptors of the analysed compounds. Moreover, the obtained toxicity was associated with the previously quantified lipophilicity of the analysed molecules. All compounds of both analysed series have pIGC50 for T. pyriformis above $-0.5 \log \mu\text{g/L}$ indicating their potential aquatic toxicity. The predicted toxicity was positively correlated with molecular weight ($p=0.025$) and molar and negatively associated with the polar surface area ($p=0.005$). The toxicity given as pIGC50 was positively correlated with predicted logD values on pH 7.4 ($p<0.001$), log P ($p<0.001$) as well as with R_M^0 values obtained with acetone-water mixture ($p<0.001$) and acetonitrile-water as mobile phase ($p<0.001$) respectively and negatively associated with the in silico predicted solubility expressed as logS ($p<0.001$). The toxic effect of the analysed succinimide derivatives increased with the increment of the lipophilicity of the succinimide core by adding more lipophilic substituents and by decrement of their aquatic solubility.

Introduction

Tetrahymena species abundance indicates a healthy aquatic environment. It is used to evaluate the toxic potential of different toxicants, pollutants and contaminants, suggests their cumulative effect and thus it is referred as an indicator of water pollution and a test system for health risk assessment [1]. Succinimide derivatives have exhibited various effects including analgetic [2], anticonvulsive [3], proapoptotic [4], antifungal [5], antibacterial and cytotoxic [6] anticancer [7,8], and also have anticholinesterase and antioxidative activity [9,10]. Two novel series of succinimide derivatives (Table 1) were tested for their antiproliferative activity and are candidates for further studying. In order to compete as drug candidates, except being safe and effective, the molecules are tested also as possible environmental pollutants together with their ability to accumulate in the environment. Assessing the risks of newly synthesized compounds to human health as well as the environmental hazards that a substance may cause is a key point for further safe application. The experimental toxicity evaluation of chemicals is not only time-consuming process with high cost but also can be ethically limited. In silico tools such as

quantitative structure–toxicity relationship (QSTR) models are applied to evaluate the toxic end-points for new or even yet not-synthesized molecules [11]. Thus, in this study 24 newly synthesized compounds were analysed for their *Tetrahymena pyriformis* toxicity in silico and their potential for aquatic toxicity was associated to their structural changes and physicochemical properties.

Experimental

Twenty-four newly synthesized succinimide derivatives of two series (thirteen from the series C and eleven from the series D, Table 1) were evaluated for their *T. Pyriformis* toxicity by the free online platform pkCSM (<http://biosig.unimelb.edu.au/pkcsm/prediction>).

Table 1. The structures of the observed succinimide derivatives

Compound	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄
C1	-CH ₃	-H	-H	-H
C2	-CH ₃	-H	-CH ₃	-H
C3	-CH ₃	-H	-OCH ₃	-H
C4	-CH ₃	-H	-OH	-H
C5	-CH ₃	-H	-COOH	-H
C6	-CH ₃	-H	-H	-COCH ₃
C7	-CH ₃	-H	-COCH ₃	-H
C8	-CH ₃	-H	-NO ₂	-H
C9	-CH ₃	-H	-Cl	-H
C10	-CH ₃	-H	-Br	-H
C11	-CH ₃	-H	-I	-H
C12	-CH ₃	-H	-H	-Cl
C13	-CH ₃	-H	-H	-Br
D1	-C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	-H	-H
D2	-C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	-OH	-H
D3	-C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	-OCH ₃	-H
D4	-C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	-COOH	-H
D5	-C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	-CN	-H
D6	-C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	-CH ₃	-H
D7	-C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	-NO ₂	-H
D8	-C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	-Cl	-H
D9	-C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	-Br	-H
D10	-C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	-H	-Cl
D11	-C ₂ H ₅	-CH ₃	-H	-Br

The method is based on the concentration of 1571 compounds which was required to inhibit 50% growth of *T. Pyriformis* (IGC50). For each compound the pIGC50, which is a negative logarithm of the concentration required to inhibit 50% growth in log µg/L, was predicted.

Values above $-0.5 \log \mu\text{g/L}$ are considered to be toxic. All compounds were drawn as 2D in ChemDraw Professional (version 16.0) their Simplified Molecular-Input Line-Entry System (SMILES) specifications were generated in order to use them for further predictions. The free online software SwissADME (<http://www.swissadme.ch/index.php>) and PreADMET (<https://preadmet.bmdrc.kr/adme/>) were applied to determine the physicochemical descriptors of the analysed compounds including molecular weight (MW), polar surface area (PSA) molar refractivity (MR), lipophilicity ($\log P$ and $\log D$ on $\text{pH}=7.4$) and aqueous solubility ($\log S$, mol/L on $\text{pH} 7.4$). Moreover, the toxicity was related to previously experimentally evaluated lipophilicity of the analysed compounds given as retention constants R_M^0 obtained on thin-layer reversed-phase chromatography with acetone-water and acetonitrile-water mixtures as mobile phases, respectively [12]. The statistical analysis was conducted with OriginPro 8.

Results and discussion

The *T. pyriformis* toxicity for all analysed compounds is given on Figure 1. All observed compounds have pIGC_{50} for *T. pyriformis* above $-0.5 \log \mu\text{g/L}$. The most polar compounds C5 and D4 with carboxylic functional group in their structure however have been predicted with the lowest toxicity levels. The predicted toxicity was positively correlated with molecular weight (adj. $r^2=0.172$, $p=0.025$) and molar refractivity (adj. $r^2=0.118$, $p=0.056$) respectively, while it was negatively correlated with the polar surface area (adj. $r^2=0.271$, $p=0.005$). Lipophilicity obtained both *in silico* and experimentally had the most significant relations indicating the lipophilicity as one of the most important descriptors for toxicity predictions. Namely, pIGC_{50} was positively correlated with predicted $\log D$ values on $\text{pH} 7.4$ (adj. $r^2=0.864$, $p=3.2 \times 10^{-11}$, Figure 2) and $\log P$ (adj. $r^2=0.506$, $p=5.92 \times 10^{-5}$) respectively, as well as with R_M^0 values obtained with acetone-water mixture as mobile phase (adj. $r^2=0.700$, $p=2.09 \times 10^{-7}$) and acetonitrile-water as mobile phase (adj. $r^2=0.801$, $p=2.10 \times 10^{-9}$, Figure 3) respectively. The toxicity pIGC_{50} of the analysed compounds on the other hand was negatively associated with the *in silico* predicted solubility expressed as $\log S$ (adj. $r^2=0.680$, $p=4.30 \times 10^{-7}$).

Figure 1. *T. pyriformis* toxicity of the analysed compounds obtained through pkCSM online tool

Figure 2. Correlation of *T. pyriformis* toxicity of the analysed compounds with in silico predicted lipophilicity expressed as logD

Figure 2. Correlation of *T. pyriformis* toxicity of the analysed compounds with experimentally obtained lipophilicity expressed as R_M^0

Conclusion

Succinimide derivatives based on QSTR analysis are expected to have pIGC50 for *T. pyriformis* above $-0.5 \log \mu\text{g/L}$. The calculated pIGC50 values for the analysed 24 succinimide derivatives can be positively associated to their lipophilicity obtained both experimentally and predicted in silico as well as negatively associated to their predicted aqueous solubility. The results indicated increased toxic effect of the compounds on *T. pyriformis* with the increment of their lipophilicity and decrement of their solubility, respectively.

References

- [1] R. Maurya, A.K. Pandey. *Sci. Total Environ.* 741 (2020) 140058.

- [2] R. Correa, V. Cechinel Filho, P. Rosa, C. Isolani Pereira, V. Schlemper, R.J. Nunes. *Pharm. Sci.* 3 (1997) 67–71.
- [3] R.R. Goehring, T.D. Greenwood, J.S. Pisipati, J.F. Wolfe. *J. Pharm. Sci.* 80 (1991) 790–792.
- [4] B. Kuran, M. Krawiecka, J. Kossakowski, M. Koronkiewicz, Z. Chilmonczyk. *Acta Pol. Pharm.* 70 (2013) 459–468.
- [5] M. Sortino, A. Postigo, S. Zacchino. *Molecules* 18 (2013) 5669–5683.
- [6] F. Zentz, R. Le Guillou, R. Labia, D. Sirot, B. Linard, A. Valla. *Farmaco* 59 (2004) 879–886.
- [7] E.L. Luzina, A.V. Popov, J. Fluor. *Chem.* 168 (2014) 121–127.
- [8] N. P. Milosevic, V. Kojic, J. Curcic, D. Jakimov, N. Milic, N. Banjac, G. Uscumlic, R. Kaliszan. *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 137 (2017) 252–257.
- [9] A.J. Guevara-Salazar, M. Espinoza-Fonseca, H.I. Beltrán, J. Correa-Basurto, D. Quintana Zavala, J.G. Trujillo-Ferrar, J.G. *J. Mex. Chem. Soc.* 51 (2007) 222–227.
- [10] A. Sadiq, F. Mahmood, F. Ullah, M. Ayaz, S. Ahmad, F. Ul Haq, G. Khan, M. Saeed *Jan.* 9 (2015) 31.
- [11] F. Abbasitabar, V. Zare-Shahabadi. *Chemosphere.* 172 (2017) 249–259.
- [12] S. Kovačević, M.K. Banjac, N. Milošević, J. Čurčić, D. Marjanović, N. Todorović, J. Krmar, S. Podunavac-Kuzmanović, N. Banjac, G. Ušćumlić. *J. Chromatogr A.* 1628 (2020) 461439.